

Evaluating integrated training for juvenile criminal justice system at the national police education and training center

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ABSTRACT

This study critically assesses the integrated technical training program for the juvenile criminal justice system, conducted by the national police education and training institute in Indonesia. The research employs a mixed-method approach, utilizing an explanatory sequential design and applying the Kirkpatrick evaluation model, involving 62 participants. Content validity is maintained through expert input, with the Aiken v formula employed for result analysis. Credibility is affirmed through a focus group discussion. The study aims to evaluate the program's impact on the rights of Indonesian children in legal conflicts. Findings indicate participants' satisfaction and high motivation at level 1 (reaction), while levels 2, 3, and 4 reveal a positive impact on protecting the rights of children involved in legal conflicts. The research highlights the need for a larger sample size and a more extended measurement period for future investigations. Objectives encompass assessing program impact, learning outcomes, behavioral changes, external organizational impact, and examining the program's practical contribution to educational research and evaluation, guiding recommendations for future improvements.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid proliferation of information technology is significantly impacting diverse facets of human life, giving rise to new behavioral patterns that may deviate from established values, norms, and legal standards. Among the most susceptible demographic to absorb, internalize, and potentially manifest such behavior are children [1]. Childhood development unfolds in three distinct phases: childhood, adolescence, and puberty [2]. During this developmental journey, children socially engage with their environment, absorbing information without fully matured abilities to filter and internalize values [3]. This vulnerable stage may lead to inner conflicts, subsequently resulting in social and legal predicaments [4], particularly categorizing a child as being in conflict with the law.

In Indonesia, the treatment of children in conflict with the law diverges from that of adults. This distinction aims to shield children from societal stigmas, safeguarding their future and contributing to national development [5]. Enforced by Law No. 11 of 2012 on the juvenile criminal justice system, with a restorative justice approach and the concept of diversion. This legal framework underscores integrated education and training, known as the SPPA training, for law enforcement officials [6], [7]. Article 92 of Law No. 11 of 2012 concerning the juvenile criminal justice system also regulates integrated education and training of SPPA training for law enforcement officials. This law is a renewal of the criminal law system in Indonesia because it is based on the perspective of improving or restoring conditions after a crime has occurred.

The Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection said that the number of child abuse from year to year tends to increase, especially in urban areas where the mobility of children's interactions is very high, especially in families, schools, public facilities, and the community. Approximately one in four children experience child abuse or neglect in their lifetime [8]. In other countries such as Ethiopia, 90% child in school has experienced some form of violence [9]. Globally, Brazil contributes high violent indicators found that regards to highest child abuse rate of children from 10 to 19 with 15-19 boys comprehending 58.3% leading to murders in the country and a femicide rate of 4.8 per 100,00 women [10]. Ally, children and adolescents experience abuse by meta-analysis estimates that 18% of girls and nearly 8% of boys. A study conducted in Cambodia, Haiti, Kenya, Malawi, Swaziland, Tanzania, and Zimbabwe indicated that over 25% of children and youth had experienced some form of violence, and the rate was as high as 37.6% among girls in Swaziland [11].

As of May 2023, there were 9,220 cases of women and children in conflict with the law. The number of victims by gender was 1,746 male victims and 8,235 female victims. Of these cases, 6,258 cases were experienced by children aged 6 to 17 years commonly referred to as the children's group (<https://keKerasaan.kemenpppa.go.id/ringkasan>). Data from the directorate general of corrections as of September 5, 2022, the number of children in conflict with the law was 1,844 children. A total of 1,137 children (62%) were in the children's special development institution (LPKA) and 707 children were in adult detention centers/prisons. The data also mentions the 6 types of crimes most commonly committed by children facing the law, namely cases of child protection/violence, theft, narcotics, abuse, murder, and others.

Even though there is Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the juvenile criminal justice system, in terms of its implementation there are still several challenges. The first PUSKAPA study states that law enforcement officers prefer to place LPKA or adult detention centers rather than in alternative detention or imprisonment facilities such as social welfare institutions (LPKS). Second, as many as 90% of children processed in court were sentenced to prison, 40% of children were detained in adult facilities and only a small proportion of cases (2%) used alternative detention. Third, in the implementation of diversion, even though it is increasingly being implemented, the impact and accountability have not been carried out transparently. Fourth, it is difficult for law enforcement officials to apply diversion because the regulations are not aligned, the threat of high penalties is high, and it is difficult to convince the victim. From the perspective of law enforcement officials, there are still many who do not understand how to settle child marriages in conflict with the law [12].

In line with these conditions, the Indonesian government issued presidential decree 175 of 2014 concerning integrated education and training for law enforcement officers and related agencies regarding the juvenile criminal justice system. This presidential regulation aims to equalize perceptions between law enforcement officers in handling children's cases. Integrated training on the juvenile criminal justice system is education and training carried out across law enforcement agencies, including the republic of Indonesia police, supreme court, attorney general's office, ministry of law and human rights, ministry of social affairs, and the Indonesian advocates association. Training on the juvenile criminal justice system is a National Priority Program from 2015 to 2025 with the following outcomes: i) increased knowledge for law enforcers and related parties regarding children's rights, restorative justice, and diversion in the juvenile criminal justice system, ii) increased competence of enforcers law and related parties in handling children in conflict with the law; and iii) the sufficient number of law enforcers and related parties in the juvenile criminal justice system.

How to find out the achievement/indicators of educational and training objectives, especially regarding increasing the competence of law enforcers in the integrated training for the juvenile criminal justice system, it is necessary to evaluate this program [13]. Evaluation is a process of searching for information, finding information, and determining information that is presented systematically about planning, values, goals, benefits, effectiveness, and suitability of something with the criteria and objectives that have been set for decision-making [14]. Implementation of evaluation is also an application of the program control function to obtain information on which points need to be repaired and improved [15].

One of the training evaluation models is the Kirkpatrick evaluation model, which was first recognized in 1959 when Donald L. Kirkpatrick wrote four series of articles entitled "techniques for evaluating training programs" which were published in training and development, the journal of the American society for training and development (ASTD) [16]. The articles describe a four-level evaluation formulated by Kirkpatrick based on concepts from his dissertation at the University of Wisconsin, Kirkpatrick put forward three specific reasons for evaluating training programs, namely: to justify the existence of a training budget by showing how the training program contributes to organizational goals and objectives. Determining whether a training program is continued or not, as well as obtaining information on how to improve future training programs. To answer these three reasons, Kirkpatrick created his four-level evaluation model which consists of level 1 (reaction), level 2 (learning), level 3 (behavior), and level 4 (result) [17].

The national police of the Republic of Indonesia entrust the management of the education and training of members of the Indonesian national police to the national police education and training institute (LemPecepatan Polri). As a leading sector, realizing human capitalism is the key to sustainable organizational excellence [18]. The national police training institute annually educates and trains 30 thousand people. All students are spread across various types and levels of education and training, including education and training in the juvenile criminal justice system [14]. The greater the number of programs, the greater the need to see how the program is being achieved. Program evaluation is not about mathematical programming, but about assessing the performance of social programs and policies [19]. Based on the background above, the research question is how effective is the implementation of the juvenile criminal justice system Training carried out by the national police education and training institute of the Republic of Indonesia.

In the realm of child justice, the prevalent challenges in Indonesia include the misalignment of regulations, law enforcement officers' preferences for specific detention facilities, and the limited use of alternative detention methods. While Law No. 11 of 2012 provides a comprehensive legal foundation, issues persist in the transparent implementation of diversion and the understanding of its significance by law enforcement officials. Previous assessments, such as the PUSKAPA study, have identified these hurdles, shedding light on the complexities surrounding the treatment of children in conflict with the law [12]. However, existing studies have not comprehensively evaluated the impact and accountability of diversion in a transparent manner. This study aims to bridge this gap by employing the Kirkpatrick evaluation model, focusing on the national police education and training institute's juvenile criminal justice system Training. Through a mixed-method approach, including questionnaires, document studies, and interviews, this research endeavors to provide a nuanced understanding of the program's efficacy, addressing the existing challenges and contributing to a more transparent, accountable, and effective approach in handling children in conflict with the law in Indonesia.

The primary objectives of this research are twofold. Firstly, to rigorously assess the effectiveness and impact of the integrated technical training program for the juvenile criminal justice system organized by the national police education and training institute. This includes evaluating participants' reactions, learning outcomes, behavioral changes, and the external impact on organizational practices. Secondly, to examine the program's practical contributions within the context of educational research and evaluation, offering insights into its positioning within the broader spectrum of human resource management development science. By systematically examining the four levels of the Kirkpatrick evaluation model, this research aims to contribute to the advancement of research and program evaluation science, shedding light on the intricacies and challenges faced in implementing such training programs. Through these objectives, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the program's strengths, weaknesses, and potential areas for enhancement, ultimately guiding recommendations for future improvements in juvenile justice education and training.

2. METHOD

This study adopts a mixed-methods research approach, as advocated by Creswell [20] who posits that a mixed-method design is optimal when either a quantitative or qualitative approach alone is insufficient to comprehensively address a research problem, and the combined strengths of both methodologies offer the most effective understanding. The research employs an explanatory sequential mix method, specifically utilizing a parallel analysis model that initiates with quantitative analysis followed by qualitative analysis [21], [22]. The research was carried out at the training batch II of 2022. The selection of research samples used a purposive sampling technique [23]. The research respondents were 62 training participants. The criteria for selecting respondents are based on the Training requirements, namely for law enforcement officers who are in the women and child protection unit. This study uses a 4-level Kirkpatrick evaluation model [24]. Data collection used was through questionnaires, interview observations and document studies at all levels, including level 1 (reaction), level 2 (learning), level 3 (behavior) and level 4 (internal impact).

2.1. Evaluation level 1 (reaction)

Evaluation at level 1, centered on participants' reactions, involves the tabulation of aspects and indicators related to participant satisfaction, as detailed in Table 1. This level assesses participants' satisfaction with the training program [25]. Success at level 1 is contingent upon trainees demonstrating high motivation and a substantial level of satisfaction with the training course. The determination of the magnitude of these two aspects employs a categorization norm formula classifying responses as low, medium, or high.

2.2. Evaluation level 2 (learning)

The evaluation of participants' learning is pivotal as it assesses the extent to which knowledge, skills, and attitudes have evolved [26]. At level 2, the evaluation incorporates learning outcomes tests and

follow-up planning rubrics. Primary data sources include pre-test and post-test results from training participants, along with the outcomes of performance assessment rubrics. Employing a pretest-posttest design, as elucidated by Bonate, enables the examination of changes in variables measured on the same experimental unit across different conditions [27]. The learning outcomes test comprises 60 items, and the assessment rubric gauges participants' follow-up plans post-training, focusing on problem-based planning and plan quality, as detailed in Table 2.

Table 2 shows the rubric scoring weight by two indicators, each with a description. The success criteria for this level entail an increase in learning outcomes, gauged by the pre and post-test results. Additionally, success in completing the follow-up plan rubric requires a minimum score of 80, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of participants' achievements and contributions to the learning process.

Table 1. Level 1 measurement aspects and indicators

SN	Aspect	Indicators
1	Participant motivation	Demonstrates a commitment to achieving maximum results Exhibits enthusiasm for facing challenges Strives for continuous improvement of abilities Displays responsibility in training participation
2	Level of satisfaction of training participants	Evaluates satisfaction with training materials Assesses satisfaction with the training instructor Gauges satisfaction with training facilities and infrastructure Judges' satisfaction with the organizer Rates satisfaction with accommodation and consumption Assesses satisfaction with health protocol

Table 2. Rubric scoring weight

SN	Indicators	Description
1	Follow-up plans based on resolving children's cases (40%)	Macro description of participants' duties aligned with their roles in the Juvenile criminal justice system Identification of problematic issues within the participant's field related to handling children Urgency in resolving identified problems Involvement of relevant parties in problem resolution Action plan detailing steps for resolution Stages outlined in the action plan
2	Quality of follow-up reports (60%)	Introductory description included Implementation strategies in the field specified Suggestions and hopes articulated

2.3. Evaluation level 3 (internal impact)

Evaluation at level 3 focuses on observing changes in behavior exhibited by trainees upon their return to their workplaces [28]. This level assesses aspects of behavioral change, including assignment placement, transfer of learning, changes in performance behavior, competency changes, and the implementation of follow-up plans as shown in Table 3. Success at level 3 is determined by a notable increase in behavioral changes, as evidenced by feedback provided through instruments completed by superiors and co-workers of the training graduates.

The success criteria for level 3 necessitate a discernible enhancement in behavioral changes. This is evaluated through the submission of instruments by the superiors and co-workers of the training graduates. These instruments serve as valuable tools for gauging the practical impact of the training program on participants' behavior in their professional settings.

Table 3. Level 3 measurement aspects and indicators

Aspect	Indicator
Behavior change	Assignment placement and transfer learning Changes in performance behavior Competency changes Implementation follow-up

2.4. Level 4 evaluation (external impact)

At level 4 (results), the organization assesses the training program's influence on employee performance, overall organizational performance, and environmental consequences [29]. This level of evaluation centers on examining the impact and benefits of the training on the organization. The level 4 evaluation measures aspects detailed in Table 4.

Before being given to the training participants, an instrument validation and reliability test was carried out. Testing the instrument's validity uses content validity to validate the question item statements through the assessment of experts (material experts, language experts, instrument experts). The results of the expert assessment were then analyzed using the Aiken's v formula to describe the level (the assessment was carried out by experts by giving a number between 1=very irrelevant to 5=very relevant) of item agreement among experts. After this stage, a focus group discussion was held (1 child criminal law expert, 1 child practitioner, and 1 program evaluator expert) as a requirement for the credibility of the instrument in the mix method. The instrument reliability test uses the Cronbach alpha formula which is more accurate because it is closer to the actual results. Quantitatively, descriptive statistics are used, the t-test difference test by calculating whether there is a significant difference in the average increase in pre-and post-test results through the t-test index [30]. Active data analysis refers to Miles and Huberman, namely data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion [3].

Table 4. Level 4 measurement aspects and indicators

Aspect	Indicator
External impact	Benefits that the organization achieves from training graduates Protection of children's rights Implementation of restorative justice Implementation of diversion Stakeholder support in the region

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Training participant profiles and discussion

The comprehensive profile of training participants, encompassing age, gender, and agency origin, is detailed in Table 5. Notably, 79% of participants originate from the police, with representation also from juvenile judges (supreme court), juvenile prosecutors (attorney general's office), community advisers (Kemenkum Ham), social workers (ministry of social affairs), and children's lawyers (Peradi). The training has direct implications for social workers, necessitating an augmentation in both the quality and quantity of their involvement [31]. The representation of each agency in implementing the training, as illustrated in Table 5, underscores the crucial objective of fostering coordination and cooperation among law enforcement officers in the field.

Table 6 outlines the age distribution of participants, revealing a predominant majority aged between 31 and 45 years. This demographic insight is pivotal for instructors, enabling the adaptation of learning methods and strategies tailored to adult learners. An andragogic/adult learning approach is employed, recognizing the wealth of experience participants bring to the training. Through collaborative sharing of experiences, valuable lessons emerge, reinforcing effective task execution [32]. In addition, through sharing and experience, lessons can be learned or entry points that will strengthen what steps and actions will be taken in carrying out the task.

Table 5. Training participant

No	Agency	Number of participants	Cumulative frequency
1	Child investigator	49	79%
2	Prosecutor	3	5%
3	Judge	1	2%
4	Community advisor	3	5%
5	Social worker	3	5%
6	Lawyer	3	5%
	Amount	62	

Table 6. Participant's age

No	Age	Number of participants	Cumulative frequency
1	20-25	9	15%
2	26-30	9	15%
3	31-35	14	23%
4	36-40	12	19%
5	41-45	10	16%
6	46-50	6	10%
7	51-55	2	3%

The gender composition of participants, presented in Table 7, discloses that 63% are male and 27% are female. In juvenile justice, gender-specific considerations are vital to address the distinct needs and experiences of male and female offenders. This includes tailored risk assessments, intervention strategies, and recognition of trauma impact [33], [34]. Remarkably, the analysis demonstrates the training program's equal effectiveness for both male and female participants, rendering gender differences inconsequential in the training's implementation.

Table 7. Participant’s gender

No	Gender	Participant	Cumulative frequency
1	Male	39	63%
2	Female	23	37%
	Amount	62	

3.2. Evaluation level 1 (reaction)

The first evaluation level encompasses participant motivation and the satisfaction of training participants, as delineated in Table 8. Analysis of all aspects in level 1 (reaction) reveals three aspects categorized as moderate—motivation, materials/subject matter, and organizers. Conversely, teachers, facilities and infrastructure, accommodation, and health protocols are categorized as high. Acknowledging these conditions, attention from Lemdiklat Polri is imperative for refining the implementation of training. Lantu *et al.* [17] posits that the evaluation at the reaction stage generally gauges perceived training, satisfaction with materials, instructors, and the training environment.

Table 8. Level 1 measurement results

SN	Aspect	Indicator	Mean	Category
1	Participant motivation	Motivation level	70.5	Medium
		Training materials	32.4	Medium
		Training instructor	32.6	High
2	Level of satisfaction of training participants	Training facilities and infrastructure	10	High
		Organizer	22	Medium
		Accommodation and consumption	5	High
		Health protocol	20	High

3.3. Evaluation level 2 (learning)

3.3.1. Pre and post test results

The learning outcomes of participants in the Integrated juvenile criminal justice system Training are elucidated in Figure 1 and detailed in Table 9. Level 2 evaluation, focusing on learning, aims to gauge the effectiveness of the instructional materials provided by the teaching staff in aligning participants' competencies with the intended expectations [14]. During this stage, standard pre and post-tests are routinely conducted to gather comprehensive insights into the evaluation of learning outcomes.

Table 9 provides insights into the evaluation of learning outcomes. The average pre-test score is 2.8, with a range from the lowest score of 1.4 to the highest value of 5.0. Following the post-test assessment, the average score significantly improves to 8.5, ranging from a low of 4.7 to a high of 9.3. The difference score, a key measure in assessing training effectiveness, highlights the notable change in performance or knowledge before and after the program [35]. The detailed results of level 2 measurements are presented in Table 10. Subsequently, a difference test is conducted, revealing a significant outcome with a p-value of 0.000. This leads to the conclusion that there is a substantial and meaningful difference in the learning outcomes of education and training participants.

Figure 1. Pre and post test results

Table 9. Level 2 measurement results

SN	Aspect	Pre test	Post test
1	The highest score	5.0	9.3
2	Lowest value	1.4	4.7
3	Average	2.8	8.5
4	Highest increase		7.00
5	Average increase		5.7

Table 10. Level 2 measurement results

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error mean	Paired differences		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
				95% confidence interval of the difference Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 learning outcomes training test	4.86935	1.99891	.17951	4.51403	5.22468	27.126	123	0.000

3.3.1. Follow-up plan assessment rubric

Figure 2 illustrates the outcomes of the rubric measurement assessing participants' proficiency in formulating follow-up plans. Rubrics serve as valuable tools for offering precise and constructive feedback on individual performance [36]. Upon closer examination of Figure 2, the overall scores fall within the range of 82-90, showcasing a commendable level of achievement. Additionally, noteworthy is the presence of participants achieving a perfect score of 100 in this particular activity.

Figure 2. Rubric measurement results

3.4. Evaluation level 3 (internal impact)

Table 11 presents the outcomes of level 3 measurement, derived from a questionnaire distributed to training graduates actively engaged in the program. The assessment covers crucial aspects such as assignment placement, transfer of learning, changes in performance behavior, competency adjustments, and the implementation of follow-up plans, providing mean results for each category.

Table 12 presents the outcomes of the interview analysis, encompassing various aspects such as assignment placement, transfer of learning, changes in performance behavior, competency adjustments, and the implementation of follow-up plans. The in-depth interviews with child investigators reveal a notable internalization and awareness, showcasing distinct changes in the behavior of training graduates actively involved in the program. Figure 3 supplements these findings, offering visual documentation of the effective implementation of follow-up plans by the training graduates participating in the SPPA training. Consistent with previous studies, these results underscore the positive impact of training programs in enhancing participants' knowledge, skills, and their ability to identify and address specific issues [37]–[39].

Table 11. Level 3 measurement results

No	Aspect	Mean
1	Assignment placement and transfer learning	46
2	Changes in performance behavior	47.7
3	Competency changes	47.4
4	Implementation of follow-up plans	43.7

Table 12. Level 3 results of interview analysis

Item	Statement	Interview answer analysis result
Assignment placement and transfer learning		
1	Currently training graduates are assigned or placed in sections/cases related to the juvenile criminal justice system	Some training graduates have changed jobs. Most of them are still placed in the PPA Polres or Polda units.
2	SPPA training is related to the training graduates' field of work	He helps a lot with tasks in the field, especially coordination and equalizing perceptions between regional legal officials
3	The knowledge that training graduates have gained during SPPA training helps training graduates in carrying out their job duties	On several occasions Training graduates were assigned to provide outreach about SPPA on local radio
4	SPPA training is in line with	Not all SPPA investigators are considered in terms of their careers.
5	Training graduates career development	Training graduates often provide understanding regarding SPPA to their colleagues and subordinates, especially when handling children's cases, they must uphold children's rights, don't let children be afraid and prioritize the success of mediation and restorative justice. There are also some training graduates who carry out informal outreach to colleagues about the juvenile criminal justice system
Changes in performance behavior		
6	Training graduates are able to apply child protection principles in handling ABH (children of perpetrators or children of victims or children of witnesses)	Prison is the last resort in law enforcement (ultimum remedium)
7	Training graduates are able to implement the knowledge and skills they have acquired during SPPA training in their daily tasks	Training graduates are able to implement the knowledge and skills they have acquired during SPPA training in their daily tasks
8	Training graduates are able to solve problems faced in carrying out their duties by applying the principles in SPPA	The SPPA Integrated Training that was attended by training graduates was very helpful in carrying out their duties at the Pare-Pare City Police because there were so many ABH cases in Pare-Pare City that a Restorative Justice approach was always sought.
9	Training graduates are able to coordinate with related parties in handling ABH	Coordination is carried out first for the interests of the child.
10	Training graduates try to put things forward	There are many cases of children dealing with the law in NTT, such as immoral acts which have been successfully carried out using a Restorative Justice approach
Competency changes		
11	Training graduates have the ability to handle children's cases by carrying out the diversion process according to SPPA according to the capacity of their duties and roles	There have been many cases of child perpetrators who have not reached court, just complete them during the investigation involving PK Bapas, Social Services, Family and Village Apparatus. However, cases of children who are victims and adult perpetrators will be investigated in detail
12	Training graduates have the ability to handle ABH (children of perpetrators or children of victims or children of witnesses) in the juvenile criminal justice process (litigation) in accordance with the provisions of the SPPA	lack of understanding regarding the handling of ABH by the victim's family who want the perpetrator to be punished severely and go to prison
13	Training graduates know and understand the age limit for criminal responsibility for children in accordance with SPPA provisions	Training graduates really understand it.
14	Training graduates are able to extract information from ABH (child victims or children of witnesses or children of perpetrators).	Investigators in handling children's cases need knowledge about children, their character, and their parents' parenting patterns.
15	Training graduates are able to analyze the causes of child delinquency related to the background of children's behavior at each age level and the importance of the role of family and environment in children's development	Handling children's cases is not easy because children in conflict with the law find it difficult to open up when asked for information, competency is needed for this. So, after attending the training, competence is formed, so that in handling cases related to children, investigators strive as much as possible for peace or restorative justice between the two parties.
16	Training graduates can provide input for improving or developing the handling of ABH (children of perpetrators or children of victims or children of witnesses) in their work environment	As an investigator who is a colleague of training graduates, I feel helped by the experience and knowledge shared. If we face a difficult child case, we usually ask for input from training graduates to help solve the case.
17	After attending SPPA training, training graduates are able to work according to their capacity in handling ABH	Training graduates work according to their capacity in handling ABH
Implementation of follow-up plans		
18	Training graduates have implemented the follow-up plan they have prepared.	The follow-up plan was coordinated with the local government and P2TP2 for a safe house for children, but it could not be implemented
19	I provide support to training graduates in implementing their follow-up plans	Some cases have been resolved by means of a media process between both parties. This was highly appreciated by the leadership
20	The follow-up plans carried out by training graduates are able to bring about changes in their work environment	Many parents thanked investigators for their case

Figure 3. Follow-up implementation activities

3.5. Evaluation level 4 (external impact)

The outcomes from the questionnaire administered to training graduates are detailed in Table 13 below. External impact evaluation is designed to gauge the extent of changes or impact that transpire within the organization following the participation of employees in training programs. This assessment of external impact involves the distribution of questionnaires not only to the training graduates but also to their colleagues and superiors. Similar practices have been adopted in previous research endeavors, which also focused on measuring external impact on training graduates, their colleagues, and superiors [40], [41]. Furthermore, a direct field survey was conducted to augment the comprehensive evaluation of the external impact.

Table 13. Level 4 measurement results

No	Aspect	Mean
1	Benefits that organizations achieve from SPPA training graduates	73.3
2	Protection of children's rights	77
3	Implementation of diversion	81
3	Implementation of restorative justice	91
4	Stakeholder support in the region	78.5

Based on the findings derived from both the questionnaire responses and direct surveys, it is evident that the SPPA training has exerted a significant external impact on the organization. Substantiating this claim are various pieces of evidence, including enhanced coordination among law enforcement officials in handling cases involving children. Noteworthy is the discovery of video evidence showcasing the collaborative efforts of SPPA training participants in safeguarding and promoting the rights of children. A compelling example is a short film set in a remote area in Murung Raya District, Central Kalimantan. This film depicts a cohesive team comprising child investigators, local government representatives, social workers, and PK Bapas, engaging in legal counseling on child protection and the juvenile justice system.

This research contributes meaningfully to the realms of educational research and evaluation. It serves as a foundational reference for the advancement of research and program evaluation science. Specifically, this study brings to light the critical position of training program evaluation science, an area that has often been overshadowed by developments in human resource management. Notable outputs of this research include the development of valuable tools such as the performance assessment rubric and the program impact measurement instrument. These instruments underwent a rigorous developmental process, involving the formulation of indicators, expert consultations, and a conclusive focus group discussion with diverse stakeholders, including child law experts, practitioners, program evaluators, Bappenas, and consultants. The entire process was fortified by the official endorsement of the head of the human resources development agency of the ministry of law and human rights of the Republic of Indonesia, affirming the guidelines and evaluation instruments for SPPA integrated training, thereby ensuring their measurability and comprehensiveness.

3.6. Recommendations for future improvement

In the pursuit of excellence and continuous enhancement in the realm of juvenile criminal justice training, this section offers key recommendations for refining and advancing the integrated technical training program. As the preceding evaluation levels shed light on the program's strengths and areas for improvement,

these recommendations serve as a strategic guide for the national police education and training center. By addressing aspects such as training content, teaching methodologies, professional development, and the overall program structure, these suggestions aim to elevate the effectiveness and impact of the training initiative. Emphasizing the importance of adaptability, collaboration, and ongoing assessment, these recommendations provide a forward-looking perspective to fortify the program's contribution to the protection of the rights of Indonesian children in conflict with the law.

To enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of the integrated technical training program for the juvenile criminal justice system, several key recommendations are proposed. First, a continuous refinement of training content is essential. Regular evaluation and updates should be conducted to align the program with evolving juvenile justice needs, incorporating emerging trends, legal amendments, and relevant case studies. Second, the adoption of innovative teaching methodologies is crucial. Exploring interactive approaches and integrating technology-based tools can accommodate diverse learning styles, fostering a more engaging and effective learning experience.

Third, prioritizing continuous professional development for instructors is paramount. Ongoing training programs should be implemented to keep instructors informed about the latest developments in juvenile justice. Building a community of practice among instructors encourages knowledge sharing and ensures continuous improvement. Fourth, future evaluations should focus on expanding the sample size and duration of the study. Increasing the number of participants enhances statistical robustness, while extending the study's duration captures longer-term impacts on participants' performance and behavior.

Fifth, stakeholder feedback should be actively incorporated into program enhancements. Soliciting input from law enforcement agencies, legal practitioners, and community organizations provides a holistic perspective, guiding adjustments to better address real-world challenges. Sixth, the establishment of a comprehensive monitoring and evaluation framework is critical. This framework will track participants' performance and behavioral changes post-training, with regular reviews to ensure alignment with program goals. Lastly, fostering collaboration with external organizations is recommended. Partnerships with entities in the juvenile justice field, academic institutions, and research centers facilitate the exchange of best practices, contributing to the overall impact and validation of the training program.

The comprehensive evaluation of the integrated technical training program for the juvenile criminal justice system has unearthed valuable insights into the program's effectiveness and impact. As we consider the achievements and areas for improvement, it is crucial to direct our attention to the future enhancements of this training initiative. To further enhance its efficacy, future iterations of the program should focus on expanding the sample size and extending the measurement duration. This will enable a more in-depth understanding of the long-term effects and sustained benefits. Moreover, continuous collaboration with experts, stakeholders, and program participants should be prioritized to refine and adapt the training content and methods. By implementing these recommendations, the integrated technical training program can continue to evolve, ensuring its enduring positive impact on the rights and well-being of Indonesian children in conflict with the law.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the evaluation of the integrated technical training program for the juvenile criminal justice system, conducted at the National Police Education and Training Center, employed a robust mixed-method approach, incorporating an explanatory sequential design and the Kirkpatrick evaluation model. With 62 participants, content validity was meticulously ensured through expert input, and the Aiken 'v' formula was utilized for results analysis. A credibility test, conducted via focus group discussions, further validated the findings. The study revealed a positive impact on the rights of Indonesian children in conflict with the law, particularly in terms of participants' satisfaction and high motivation at level 1 (reaction). Additionally, the integrated technical education and training for the juvenile criminal justice system exhibited substantial influence on levels 2, 3, and 4, indicating a tangible contribution to the protection of the rights of Indonesian children facing legal challenges. As a recommendation for future research, a larger sample size and an extended measurement time could enhance the depth and breadth of insights into the program's long-term effectiveness and sustained impact.

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